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ANTIFUNGAL EFFECT OF *LACTUCA TATARICA* AND *LACTUCA SERRIOLA* PLANT EXTRACTS TO SOME PHYTOPATHOGENIC FUNGI¹Shukurlu Emil Namik, ²Aleskerova Adila Novruz, ³Bakhshaliyeva Konul Farrukh^{1,2}Institute of Botany, Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan,
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Summary. *The rapid growth of the human population puts a huge strain on the agricultural industry. Fungal phytopathogens are one of the main causes of agricultural crop loss. Although pesticide usage seems to solve this issue, it has a deleterious effect on human health and the ecological environment. Some of the plant-derived substances that have an antifungal effect might solve this problem. In this study, the antifungal activity of the aerial parts of *Lactuca tatarica* and *Lactuca serriola* and their crude ethanolic extracts have been investigated against 3 fungal phytopathogens: *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium acuminatum*, and *Alternaria solani*. The aerial parts of *L. serriola* and *L. tatarica* demonstrated an inhibitory effect only against *A. solani*. The crude ethanolic extract of the aerial parts of both plant species had an antifungal effect on *A. solani* and *F. acuminatum*. Moreover, the crude extracts have exhibited a slightly inhibitory effect against *A. flavus*.*

Keywords: *Lactuca*, phytopathogens, ethanolic extract, antifungal activity, biopesticides.

Introduction. Food security is one of the priority policies of the governments. Despite the technological developments, the increase rate of the world population keeps on advancing faster than food production. By 2050, the world's population is expected to reach 9.8 billion, a 22.5 % increase from now, with the majority of that growth will be in countries with low to low-middle incomes. Because of the rising cost of living and the consequent need to feed a larger, more urban population, meat and cereal production must increase by 70% each. Furthermore, the world's climate continues to deteriorate, placing considerable strain on the systems currently in place for producing food and fiber. Too much work could be done with regard to the fair distribution of current food production and to prevent globally occurring food waste. Approximately a third of all produced food is wasted [1]. It is obvious that food security will require a growth in sustainable agricultural production especially in the production of cereals (wheat, rice, and maize) [2]. In developing countries, expanding the agricultural sector is viewed as crucial to achieving development goals. It is clearer than ever before that new technology must be used in the agriculture sector after years of the green revolution and a drop in the ratio of agricultural products to global population increase [3]. Due to losses caused by pathogens, pests, and diverse abiotic stresses including waterlogging and drought the actual on-farm yields are often below the potential yield. The impacts of pathogens and pests are exacerbated with the high temperatures that are induced by global warming. Breeding more disease-resistant and pest-resistant varieties is still a cost-effective way to raise global food production [1]. Production is severely hampered by biotic stressors such as necrotrophic and biotrophic fungal, bacterial, and viral pathogens. For instance, a new race of *Puccinia graminis*, the cause of stem rust, defeated the race-specific resistance gene Sr31 that was present in 70% of wheat cultivars in eastern Africa in 1999 [4]. The stripe rust pathogen *Puccinia striiformis*, appeared in the USA in 2000 and caused epidemics across the Midwest [5]. *Magnaporthe oryzae*, the rice blast fungus, is responsible for a field disease of wheat that was found in Brazil in 1985 [6]. These examples

emphasize the urgent need to understand perfectly crop–pathogen interactions and how this knowledge can be put into practice in agricultural strategies. There is two-way communication involved in the interactions between a plant and its diseases. On the one hand, plants must be able to recognize and protect themselves against a potential pathogen settling down on their surface, on the other hand, the pathogen must be able to manipulate the plant biology in order to form an appropriate environment for its development and reproduction [2].

In this article, we focused on fungal plant pathogens. The genus *Aspergillus*, which is a member of the phylum *Ascomycota*, comprises over 185 known species. About 20 of them have been related to dangerous infections in both people and animals. *Aspergillus flavus* is perhaps the most notorious species of this genus. It is the second most frequent cause of invasive and non-invasive aspergillosis in humans and animals, and it is the main cause of aspergillosis in some geographical locations. *A. flavus* is one of the most prevalent and widespread soil-borne moulds in nature, and it can be found anywhere on the planet. It is a saprophytic fungus that can survive on a variety of organic nutrient sources, including plant debris, decaying wood, animal fodder, compost piles, stored grains, outdoor, and indoor air environments (air ventilation systems). The secondary metabolites that *A. flavus* produces include aflatoxins, which are the most toxic and carcinogenic natural substances known to cause aflatoxicosis and induce cancers in mammals. Additionally, it contaminates many crops (including cotton, peanuts, and corn) with aflatoxins. This pervasive mould not only lowers crop productivity but also reduces the quality of the harvested grains [7].

Next experimented plant pathogenic fungi is *Fusarium acuminatum*. In agricultural settings, *F. acuminatum* regularly appears and is frequently isolated from the roots and stems of various crops. Examples include alfalfa, maize, wheat, soybeans and bananas. *F. acuminatum* has typically been viewed a saprophyte and a secondary colonizer of agricultural plants [8]. The significance of *Fusarium* species is estimated through damages that they cause either by devastating crops, grain, stored fruits or by causing the reduction in the livestock production or death of animals. The majority of *Fusarium* species can cause mycoses in plants, animals, and people, as well as mycotoxicoses in both animals and people. These fungal species parasitize on tissues and living cells that are weakened by other factors and cause infections. These fungi produce mycotoxins in infected plants, and if those plants are part of a food chain, they can make people and animals intoxicated. This condition is referred to as a mycotoxicosis [9]. The T-2 toxin is produced by *F. acuminatum* and that is the most toxic representative of trichothecene mycotoxins [10].

Another fungus that we experimented on belongs to the genus *Alternaria*. The species like *A. solani*, *A. alternate*, *A. porri*, and *A. dauci* affect their respective hosts by causing various diseases. *A. solani* is the most destructive and causes Early Blight of potato and tomato. It causes illnesses on stems of seedlings, and adult plants, fruits of tomato. Producers of tomatoes suffer losses each year as a result of the early blight disease. Fungicides like mancozeb, benomyl, captafol and carbendazim are the most popular way for controlling these pathogens [11]. Almost 45% of the annual food production is lost because of pest infestation. Therefore, effective pest management by using pesticides is necessary to combat pests and to boost the crop production. A number of pesticides, including chlordane, dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT), endrin, mirex, dieldrin, heptachlor and hexachlorobenzene and aldrin have negative effects on both human health and the environment [12]. Plant pathogenic fungi have been successfully controlled using synthetic fungicides. Their prolonged usage has disrupted natural biological systems and occasionally led to the development of fungus resistance. They caused problems for the environment and human health and had negative effects on organisms that were not their intended targets [13]. Uncontrolled use of pesticides has led to a number of issues, including adverse effects on human health, adverse effects on pollinating insects, contamination of soil and its direct and indirect impact on ecosystems. Pesticides are typically sprayed as a preventative

measure, which results in residual toxicity and environmental risks. On the other hand, applying pesticides after the onset of a disease results in some crop losses [3].

As a result, alternative crop protection strategies have been developed. In order to limit the use of synthetic fungicides, intensive researches into the possible exploitation of biopesticides have been undertaken. Botanical fungicide development could lessen the drawbacks of synthetic counterparts, such as environmental pollution and resistance. Botanical fungicides may be less toxic to the environment, effective and biodegradable in this regard. Biopesticides are generally categorized as natural products (animal-derived, microorganism-derived and higher plant-derived products) and microorganisms (protozoa, nematodes, bacteria, fungi and viruses) [13]. Because biopesticides can be effectively utilized in sustainable agricultural practices, their usage has recently gained momentum [14]. Cinnamaldehyde, jojoba oil, laminarin and milsana are some of the examples of plant-derived biopesticides. Cinnamaldehyde, which is isolated from a cinnamon essential oil, is effective against dollar spot caused by *Sclerotinia homeocarpa*, dry bubble caused by *Verticillium fungicola* and pitch canker disease caused by *Fusarium moniliforme var. subglutinans*. Jojoba oil has an ability to maintain its stability even at high temperatures and this feature makes it a widely usable fungicide in almost all climatic conditions. One of its action mechanisms is to form a physical barrier between the leaf surface and an insect pest. Laminarin is found in the blue-green algae *Laminaria digitata* and it successfully triggers defense reactions in grapevine plants against downy mildew and gray mold caused by *Plasmopara viticola* and *Botrytis cinerea*, respectively. Milsana is an ethanol extract of *Reynoutria sachalinensis* and intended for use on greenhouse-grown plants. Milsana is used for prevention rather than a curative application. Its main target disease is powdery mildew [13]. The phytochemical studies of plants of genus *Lactuca* L. demonstrated the presence of a variety of plant metabolites including triterpenoids, phenolics, saponins, lignans, coumarins, phytosterols, and sesquiterpene lactones. These phytochemical substances are directly responsible for the medicinal activity of the respective species in the treatment of several disorders [15]. *L. serriola* has been used in folk medicine for the treatment of gastrointestinal and respiratory diseases along with several other ailments [16]. *L. tatarica* is traditionally used in folk medicine in some Asian countries against internal wounds, joint pains, abdominal distension and skin bacterial infection (erysipelas) [17]. As phytochemical compounds are responsible for the usage of these species in traditional medicine, they could be effective against plant fungal pathogens. Therefore, the antifungal activity of the raw aerial parts of *L. serriola* and *L. tatarica* and their crude ethanolic extracts is investigated in this research.

The actuality of the subject. Fungal plant pathogens are one of the main causes of the loss of crops in agriculture. Synthetic pesticides have a detrimental effect on human health and environment. Novel plant-derived biopesticides may sort this issue out.

The purpose of the study. *L. tatarica* and *L. serriola* are the investigated plants in this research. The aim of this study is to investigate the antifungal effect of the aerial parts and the ethanolic extracts obtained from them against *Fusarium acuminatum*, *Alternaria solani* and *Aspergillus flavus*.

The object of research. *Lactuca tatarica* (L.) C.A.Mey. (blue lettuce) and *Lactuca serriola* L. (prickly lettuce) plant species.

Materials and Methods

Plant material. The aerial parts of *L. tatarica* were collected on summer, in 2022 from the Novkhany village, Absheron region of Azerbaijan (40°34'31.27"N, 49°46'17.91"E; 27 m below sea level). Regards to the *L. serriola*, its aerial parts were collected on summer, in 2022 from the Novkhany village, Absheron region of Azerbaijan (40°34'24.36"N, 49°46'17.26 "E; 20 m below sea level). Collected materials were stored at room temperature avoiding contact with direct sunlight until use.

Extraction procedure. 300 g finely chopped and dried raw materials (leaves and stems) of *L. serriola* and *L. tatarica* are used as a research objects. Cold maceration is done at room temperature by mixing the plant with ethanol (96%) [18]. The extracts was decanted and filtered. Then concentrated by rotary evaporator on the water bath (evaporator model: ROVA-N2L (MRC, Israel); water bath model: WB-2000 (ANM Industries, India)). The procedure is repeated thrice. 35.09 g of dried extract of the aerial parts of *L. tatarica* is obtained and the percentage yield was 11.69 %. Regards to the aerial parts of *L. serriola*, 12.54 g of the dried extract is obtained, thus the percentage yield was 4.18 %. The dried crude extracts were then stored in the fridge at -7.3 °C until use.

Antifungal activity. The plant extracts were tested against three important fungal pathogens: *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium acuminatum* and *Alternaria solani*. These microorganisms were provided by the local culture stock of the Institute of Microbiology, Ministry of Science and Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan. In order to determine the antifungal activity of the presented plant and the dry extracts obtained from them, the experiments were carried out at the following stages:

1. *L. serriola*, *L. tatarica* plant materials were crushed and moistened, placed in Petri dishes and sterilized for 30 minutes under a pressure of 0.5 atm. Then, fungal cultures of *A. flavus*, *F. acuminatum* and *A. solani* were added to those containers in equal amounts and cultivated in a thermostat with a temperature of 28 °C for 7 days [19]. Agarified malt juice was used as a control.

2. In the second stage, 0.5% dry extract was added to the Czapek nutrient medium, and then the above-mentioned cultures were planted. As a control, Czapek nutrient medium without any added dry extract was used. Then these also kept in a thermostat for 7 days with a temperature of 28°C [20]. The composition of the Czapek medium was 1 g of K_2HPO_4 , 2 g of $NaNO_3$, 0.5 g of KCl , 0.01 g of $FeSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, 0.5 g of $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, 30 g of Saccharose, 16 g of Agar in 1000 ml of distilled water [21].

The developed fungal biomass of first and second stages were calculated.

Results and Discussion

The antifungal effect of *L. serriola*, *L. tatarica* plant species and their crude extracts on microscopic phytopathogenic fungi is studied. The effect of the plant material and its crude extracts against *A. flavus*, *F. acuminatum*, *A. solani* fungi was determined. As indicated, *F. acuminatum* and *A. solani* are fungi that cause pathologies in plants. *A. flavus*, in addition to causing pathologies, also has a toxic effect. The results are comparatively demonstrated in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1. Antifungal effect of the plant materials on tested fungi.

Figure 2. Antifungal activity of crude ethanolic extracts on tested fungi.

The effect of crude ethanolic extracts on fungi is more effective than the used plant materials. Thus, the development of all three fungi was relatively low in comparison with those in controls. In both plants, the main inhibitory effect is observed against *A. solani* fungus. Although the dried ethanolic extract of both plants had an antifungal effect on all fungi, the most significant effect was against the fungus *F. acuminatum*. Finally, compared to the control, both *L. serriola* and *L. tatarica* plant materials in Petri dishes affected only *A. solani*, while the dry extract of the plant aerial parts had an antifungal effect on both *A. solani* and *F. acuminatum*. Although the plant material did not inhibit the development of *A. flavus* but the crude extracts have demonstrated a slightly inhibitory effect against it.

Phytochemical substances play a major role on antifungal activities. Extracts of turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) showed antifungal activity against *A. flavus* and reduced aflatoxin B1 production [22]. The extracts obtained from *Aloe vera* leaves demonstrated the antifungal effect on *A. flavus* [23]. The essential oil of *Origanum acutidens* and its components (carvacrol, thymol p-cymene) inhibited the growth of *A. solani* and *F. acuminatum* [24]. A flavonoid quercetin is detected in the aerial parts of *L. serriola* [25]. In one study, quercetin that is detected in ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) rhizome extract has showed significant inhibitory activity against *F. solani* [26]. Lupeol that belongs to the triterpenes has been detected in the roots of *L. serriola* [16] and it has exhibited antifungal activity against *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Penicillium notatum* [27].

Conclusion

Synthetic pesticide usage has caused environmental contamination. Plant-derived substances might be an alternative substitute. Up to the present, numerous plant metabolites with different chemical structures have been found to have antifungal properties. A little number of botanical fungicides have been commercialized, but due to intensive research, many products would be developed. The results of this research open up new horizons for further studies on biopesticide development including the isolation of the compounds responsible for the antifungal activity present in *L. tatarica* and *L. serriola*.

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Противогрибковая активность экстрактов растений *Lactuca tatarica* и *Lactuca serriola* на некоторые фитопатогенные грибы

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Резюме. Стремительный рост населения ложится тяжелым бременем на сельскохозяйственную отрасль. Грибные фитопатогены являются одной из основных причин порчи сельскохозяйственной продукции. Хотя использование пестицидов решает эту проблему, оно оказывает негативное влияние на здоровье человека и экологическую среду. Некоторые растительные компоненты с противогрибковым эффектом могут решить эту проблему. В данной работе изучено противогрибковое действие надземных частей растений *Lactuca tatarica* и *Lactuca serriola* и их спиртовых сухих экстрактов в отношении 3-х фитопатогенных грибов: *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium acuminatum* и *Alternaria solani*. Надземные части *L. serriola* и *L. tatarica* проявляли ингибирующее действие только в отношении *A. solani*. Сухие экстракты, полученные с этанолом из надземных частей обоих видов растений, оказывали противогрибковое действие на *A. solani* и *F. acuminatum*. Кроме того, сухие экстракты проявляли слабое ингибирующее действие в отношении *A. flavus*.

Ключевые слова: *Lactuca*, фитопатогены, этанольный экстракт, антифунгальная активность, биопестициды.

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***Lactuca tatarica* və *Lactuca serriola* bitki ekstraktlarının bəzi fitopatogen göbələklərə qarşı antifunqal təsiri**

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Xülasə. İnsan əhalisinin sürətli artımı kənd təsərrüfatı sənayesi üzərinə böyük yük qoymaqladır. Funqal fitopatogenlər kənd təsərrüfatı məhsullarına vurulan zərərin əsas səbəblərindən biridir. Pestisidlərin istifadəsi bu problemi həll etsə də, onlar insan sağlamlığına və ekoloji mühitə mənfi təsir göstərir. Antifunqal təsiri olan bəzi bitki mənşəli komponentlər bu problemi həll edə bilər. Bu tədqiqatda *Lactuca tatarica* və *Lactuca serriola* bitkilərinin yerüstü hissələrinin və onların etanolla alınmış quru ekstraktlarının 3 fitopatogen göbələyə qarşı antifunqal təsiri öyrənilmişdir: *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium acuminatum* və *Alternaria solani*. *L. serriola* və *L. tatarica*-nın yerüstü hissələri yalnız *A. solani*-yə qarşı inhibitor təsir göstərmişdir. Hər iki bitki növünün yerüstü hissələrindən etanolla alınmış quru ekstraktlar *A. solani* və *F. acuminatum*-a göbələk əleyhinə təsir göstərmişdir. Bundan əlavə, quru ekstraktlar *A. flavusa* qarşı zəif inhibitor təsir göstərmişdir.

Açar sözlər: *Lactuca*, fitopatogenlər, etanollu ekstrakt, antifunqal aktivlik, biopestisidlər.

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